

Coordination Plan

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DELIVERABLE 1.1, V2.0 (Post-review revision)

MeDeMAP – Mapping Media for Future Democracies

Grant Agreement number: 101094984

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Document information

Project information	
Grant Agreement no.	101094984
Funding scheme	Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions
Project title	Mapping Media for Future Democracies
Project acronym	MeDeMAP
Project starting date	01/03/2023
Document information	
Work package no.	1
Work package title	Coordination
Work package lead beneficiary	OEAW
Task(s)	1.1
Deliverable no.	1.1
Deliverable title	Coordination Plan
Deliverable type	Other
Contractual date of deliverable	30/04/2024
Actual date of deliverable	31/08/2024 (V2.0)
Editor(s)	-
Author(s)	Josef Seethaler (OEAW), Olha Drozd (OEAW)
Reviewer(s)	-
Version	2.0
Status	Final
Total number of pages (including cover)	40
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Abstract	<p>With this plan work within all work packages is coordinated and consolidated throughout the project duration. It ensures that all necessary steps will be planned and synchronized to achieve the goals of the project within the different phases. Continuous work planning will be a major tool to ensure project contingency. This plan will be continuously adjusted to best serve the goals of the project.</p>

Document history

Version	Date	Submitted by	Changes
V1.0	30/04/2023	OEAW	Initial version
V2.0	31/08/2024	OEAW	Deliverable submission process (3.2) revised Post-review revision: Risk management (6.1) updated; minor errors corrected

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1 Introduction and Overview

1.1 Purpose and Scope of this Document

The objective of this Coordination Plan is to provide a detailed description of MeDeMAP's work packages, task start-ups, deliverables, project meetings, and documents, including risk and cost/schedule management. The purpose of this document is to ensure efficient coordination and collaboration among the consortium members, in compliance with MeDeMAP's Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement.

Chapter 1 outlines MeDeMAP's project organization and governance structure, while Section 1.3 covers gender issues in accordance with the [European Commission's strategy on gender equality in research and innovation policy](#).

Chapter 2 breaks down MeDeMAP's project structure into person-months, work packages, tasks, deadlines, and partners involved in each task.

Chapter 3 provides an overview of all deliverables, followed by the submission process and quality assurance procedure of the deliverables in Sections 3.2 and 3.3, respectively.

Chapter 4 addresses the organization of project meetings within and outside the consortium.

Chapter 5 presents guidelines for information and documentation management, including access to a common communication and collaboration tool.

Chapter 6 addresses risk management and conflict resolution pathways in Section 6.1 and 6.2, respectively.

Chapter 7 covers cost and schedule management.

1.2 Project Organization

The Call "Media for democracy – democratic media" (HORIZON-CL2-2022-DEMOCRACY-01) has been made as part of the Horizon Europe Programme "Culture, creativity and inclusive society – Democracy and Governance" and in the context of the [European Democracy Action Plan](#) (EDAP), which is designed to empower citizens and build more resilient democracies across the EU by promoting free and fair elections, strengthening media freedom and countering disinformation. Other related initiatives and instruments of the European Commission are the [Digital Services Act](#) (DSA), the [Digital Markets Act](#) (DMA) and the [Media Freedom Act](#) (MFA).

Inspired by these documents, the project is concerned with the current state and future prospects of the political information environment in the European Union. It is therefore interested in the extent to which certain media perform which democratic functions for which audiences under which conditions. In exploring these guiding questions, it will cover

- (1) **various notions of democracy** as they exist in European societies,
- (2) the **entire range of news media**, regardless of distribution channel, mandate, ownership and source of financing,

- (3) the **legal and (self-)regulatory framework** under which media houses and journalists operate and people use media,
- (4) the media's potential to promote and support political participation (**supply side**),
- (5) and the media use patterns, communication needs and democratic attitudes of the audiences (**demand side**).
- (6) The results will be confronted with **citizens' visions of future media landscapes**.

An innovative multi-method design consisting of large-scale quantitative analyses, in-depth qualitative approaches and participatory action research will be applied. Analyses should be based on the most recent data available; given the project start date in February 2023, this will typically be data from 2022. If data from 2022 are not available, data from the nearest past year must be used.

- The findings will be used to create a **multi-layer map of European political information environments**.
- By comparing the map's layer, conclusions can be drawn from congruencies and discrepancies between them, **good practice examples** can be identified, and **guidelines for stakeholders** can be derived.

This analytical concept results in five scientific work packages, which are concerned with democratic theory (WP2), the legal & self-regulatory framework (WP3), media supply (WP4), the demand side (WP5), and a work package where supply meets demand – or, perhaps, where supply and demand collide (WP6). In addition, WP1 supervises all legal, financial, and administrative issues (including ethical requirements and GDPR matters), monitors the research progress (including data handling) and is responsible for creating the proposed map of European political information environments. WP7 is responsible for internal and external communications as well as for dissemination and exploitation of results (Figure 1).

Figure 1

WP Structure According to the Analytical Concept of the Project

Research in the five scientific work packages is structured in phases and closely linked to each other. Figure 2 illustrates the dependencies and interrelations between the work packages at the levels of objectives, outcomes, and impact, and Figure 3 at the level of tasks; so that the activities in all WPs will benefit from each other.

Figure 2

Relationships Between Work Packages, Objectives, Outcomes and Impact of the Project

Regarding the **timing of the project**, in the **first phase** (coinciding with the first year of the project), WP3, WP4 and WP5 deal with wide-scale quantitative inquiries in their respective fields of research. The data collection is based on secondary data and will be carried out on a European level. This data also represents the most basic layers of the envisaged map. During this phase, WP2 is developing a theoretical framework, based on democratic theory, and, building on this, analytical models to study media supply and demand as well as the legal and regulatory context of both sides.

These models will be applied, in the **second phase**, to first-hand, qualitative research on media regulation, media production and media audiences, that will be carried out in the ten countries represented in the Consortium. Data from qualitative research will allow for a refinement of the map, but, above all, the results of in-depth analyses will allow for a thorough assessment of regulatory frameworks from the perspective of securing and strengthening a democratic media system; of the relationships between production conditions and the democratic functions of the media, focusing on political participation through and in the media; and of media practices, the state of people's trust in the news media and democratic institutions, and their expectations of media and democracy. Moreover, a reanalysis of existing empirical data and of project's

interventions will allow for an empirical enrichment of the theoretical framework and for a theory-driven understanding of how democracy is perceived and practiced in the European Union. In parallel to the second phase, WP6 starts preparing the theory-informed implementation of citizens' parliaments (using Participatory Action Research as methodological approach) to learn more about the qualities that a future media ecosystem should have from a bottom-up perspective, thus involving citizens in the co-creation of the agenda for the development and the content of a "media map for future democracies". Figure 3 shows the tasks and timeline of the project.

Figure 3
Relationships Between Work Packages and Tasks on the Timeline

1.3 Governance Structure

MeDeMAP features a consortium of actors from a variety of countries and policy contexts in Europe and with an exceptional breadth of disciplinary expertise. This ensures the highest possible quality of knowledge deployed and produced. In order to manage this large project, a specific management framework has been built, ensuring good governance, information exchange, and clearly defined responsibilities. MeDeMAP's formal governance structure comprise

- the **General Assembly** as the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium,
- the **Steering Committee** as the supervisory body for the execution of the project, which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly,
- the **Coordinator** as the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the legal entities involved in the action that are parties to the Grant Agreement and the Granting Authority.

The General Assembly shall consist of one representative of each of the following ten parties to the Grant Agreement:

- 1 OEAW - OESTERREICHISCHE AKADEMIE DER WISSENSCHAFTEN (AT)
- 2 CU - UNIVERZITA KARLOVA (CZ)
- 3 IULM - LIBERA UNIVERSITA DI LINGUE E COMUNICAZIONE IULM (IT)
- 4 JU- UNIWERSYTET JAGIELLONSKI (PL)
- 5 COMMIT - COMMUNITY MEDIEN INSTITUT FÜR WEITERBILDUNG, FORSCHUNG UND BERATUNG (AT)
- 6 Lusófona Uni - COFAC COOPERATIVA DE FORMACAO E ANIMACAO CULTURAL CRL (PT)
- 7 TLU - TALLINN UNIVERSITY (EE)
- 8 IMT - INSTITUT MINES-TELECOM (FR)
- 9 MIC - MARY IMMACULATE COLLEGE (IE)
- 10 MI - MIROVNI INSTITUT (MI)

The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the General Assembly, unless decided otherwise in a meeting of the General Assembly.

The Steering Committee shall consist of the Coordinator and the leaders of the work packages:

- 1 Josef Seethaler (coordinator, leader WP1 and WP3)
- 2 Nico Carpentier (leader WP2)
- 3 Beata Klimkiewicz (leader WP4)
- 4 Andrea Miconi (leader WP5)
- 5 Helmut Peissl (leader WP6)
- 6 Manuel José Damásio (leader WP7)

The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the Steering Committee. In case of incapacity, the Coordinator has the right to authorize a WP leader to lead the meeting.

The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as beneficiary, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement, Article 7, and the Consortium Agreement.

The responsibilities of the beneficiaries are described in the Grant Agreement, Article 7, and in the Consortium Agreement.

The tasks and operational procedures for the Consortium Bodies are described in the Consortium Agreement.

Sometimes it may be necessary to discuss specific questions on definitions of research objects and methodological tools in a larger circle of partners. For this purpose, so-called **Task Forces** can be established.

Task Forces should be chaired by those WP leaders in whose WP such a question has been raised. Since these are basically problems that need to be solved quickly, a quick and targeted procedure should be applied. Therefore, it is suggested that the leader of a task force (1.) invites partners to participate in the discussion, and (2.) provides a problem description with concrete proposals for solutions. These proposed solutions should then be commented on in a virtual meeting of Task Force members or in the form of written comments by the Task Force members within a given deadline. Finally, it is up to the WP leader to decide which solution to use.

1.4 Gender Issues

Gender issues will be taken into account in project management, implementation and dissemination in line with the EC gender equality strategy. Project management and implementation will ensure that the gender dimension is appropriately integrated into interventions, surveys, composition of focus groups and citizens' parliaments, involvement of stakeholders, and data collection in general. Dissemination activities will strive to use gender-neutral language, and gender-relevant results will be labelled as such in press releases and other communications. Communication tools will be checked to make them inclusive for all and overcome gender blindness. For more information see Part B of the Grant Agreement.

2 Project Structure

Looking at the project as a whole (Chapter 1.2), it becomes evident that there are dependencies and interrelations between all work packages at all levels. The arrangement of tasks within the work packages always follows the same pattern: from quantitative to qualitative research and then to an evaluative synopsis of the results of both methodological approaches. This also implies that the tasks do not only depend directly on each other inside the respective work package, but the input from many tasks is also required in other work packages. This should facilitate parallel work in several work packages but requires all partners to have the particular topics in mind, which in turn makes the aforementioned dependencies and interrelationships between the work packages more obvious and fruitful. In any case, communication between WP leaders (who make up the Steering Committee) as well as between WP leaders and partners is crucial, and a strong coordination within and between the various work packages is demanded.

2.1 Project Structure Breakdown

The list of work packages is shown in Table 1. The information flow in the MeDeMAP consortium is presented in Figure 4, which gives an overview of all work tasks that are part of the project. On the left side of the Figure, a list of WPs and all tasks included in each WP can be found together with the starting date and the duration of each task. Most WPs run throughout the project, with the exception of WP 3 and 6. WP 3 deals with the legal and regulatory foundations of media supply and demand; it runs only in the first half of the project. WP 6 builds on the research findings of all the other scientific WPs. Hence it starts not until the middle of the project.

Table 1

Work Packages

WP No.	WP Title	Lead Participant No.	Lead Participant Short Name	Person-Months	Start Month	End Month
1	Coordination	1	OEAW	39,00	1	36
2	Theoretical embedding	2	CU	33,00	1	36
3	Legal and (self-)regulatory framework	1	OEAW	34,00	1	20
4	The supply side	4	JU	79,00	1	36
5	The demand side	3	IULM	73,00	1	36
6	Supply meets demand	5	COMMIT	49,00	17	36
7	Dissemination, exploitation and communication	6	Lusófona Uni	70,00	1	36
				377,00		

Figure 4
Timing of Work Packages and Tasks

In order to facilitate coordination, MeDeMAP's distribution of person-months (PM) places the responsibility and, accordingly, a great number of PMs with the WP leaders (Table 2). On the other hand, there are various categories of partners within the WPs according to the expertise of each partner: partners with high involvement (with around ten PMs), partners with medium involvement (with around five PMs) and low involvement (with 2 PMs). However, this basically promising approach has the disadvantage that some tasks may prove too ambitious in relation to the number of PMs. The WP leaders, therefore, have developed concrete work plans, so that partners with a small number of PMs in a given WP do not run the risk of getting into an awkward situation. This is described within the context of the various work packages.

Table 2
Staff Effort per Participant

Participant	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	Total Person-Months
1 - OEAW	18.00	2.00	12.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	10.00	48.00
2 - CU	2.00	25.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	9.00	4.00	46.00
3 - IULM	4.00	2.00	2.00	5.00	25.00	4.00	4.00	46.00
4 - JU	2.00	2.00	6.00	27.00	2.00	2.00	4.00	45.00
5 - COMMIT	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	16.00	4.00	30.00
6 - Lusófona Uni	7.00		2.00	10.00	10.00	2.00	28.00	59.00
7 - TLU	1.00		2.00	10.00	10.00		4.00	27.00
8 - IMT	1.00		2.00	11.00	10.00		4.00	28.00
9 - MIC	1.00		2.00	5.00	5.00	7.00	4.00	24.00
10 - MI	1.00		2.00	5.00	5.00	7.00	4.00	24.00
Total Person-Months	39.00	33.00	34.00	79.00	73.00	49.00	70.00	377.00

2.2 Work Packages

The following descriptions of the work packages are based on information provided by the WP leaders. They will be continuously updated.

2.2.1 Work Package 1: Coordination

WP title:	Coordination									
WP No.	1									
Lead beneficiary	OEAW									
Work package leader	Josef Seethaler									
Start month	1									
End month	36									
Participant number:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name participant:	OEAW	CU	IULM	JU	COMMIT	Lusófona Uni	TLU	IMT	MIC	MI
PM per participant:	18.00	2.00	4.00	2.00	2.00	7.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Tasks/participant	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3	1-3	2	2	2	2

Objectives: WP1 provides the central project management activities running during the entire course of the project.

The first task of WP1 deals with the **legal, financial and administrative coordination** of the project. According to the Grant Agreement, the Coordinator must:

1. monitor that the action is implemented properly,
2. act as the intermediary for all communications between the consortium and the granting authority, and in particular:
 - a. request and review any documents or information required and verify their quality and completeness before passing them on to the granting authority,
 - b. submit the deliverables and reports to the granting authority,
 - c. inform the granting authority about the payments made to other beneficiaries,
3. distribute the payments received from the granting authority to the other beneficiaries.

In addition, the first version of the **Data Management Plan (D1.2)** will be provided in Month 6, but it is likely that this plan will evolve during the lifetime of the project to present the status of the project's reflections on data management.

T1.2 concerns the **supervision of the research progress**, including accomplishment of the research and technical objectives, quality management (see Chapter 3.3), preparation and chairing of meetings, monitoring implementation of decisions taken at meetings, ensuring knowledge transfer among work packages and to different stakeholders. Particularly, the Coordinator is responsible for delivering two periodic reports (D1.5 = M14, D1.8 = M36; see Chapter 7) and policy papers for different stakeholders (D1.7 = M36). The last two subtasks mentioned will be performed in cooperation with all partners, particularly in coordination with WP7.

A special MeDeMAP task (T1.3, running M10-36) is the **creation and maintenance of a multi-layer map of European political information environments**. Here, two phases can be distinguished: the first phase until the completion of the quantitative data input (D1.3 = M15) and the completion of the front end in cooperation with WP7 (D1.4 = M18; at that time, the map of European political information environments will be made publicly available), and the second phase with the refinement of the map, expansion of quantitative data for the EU-27, especially across time, and the visualization of the information from the qualitative analysis covering the ten countries of the consortium (D1.6 = M32). The data input is done in cooperation with the leaders of WP3, WP4 and WP5.

2.2.2 Work Package 2: Theoretical Embedding

WP title:	Theoretical embedding									
WP No.	2									
Lead beneficiary	CU									
Work package leader	Nico Carpentier									
Start month	1									
End month	36									
Participant number:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name participant:	OEAW	CU	IULM	JU	COMMIT	Lusófona Uni	TLU	IMT	MIC	MI
PM per participant:	2.00	25.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	-	-	-	-	-
Tasks/participant	2-3	1-4	2-3	2-3	4	-	-	-	-	-

Objectives: WP2 aims to establish a state-of-the-art understanding of the current shift in how democracy is perceived and practiced in the European Union, at its many levels. Considering the ongoing shifts in what democracy means, how it should work and what democratic government is all about, WP2 reflects on the one hand, on the diversity of meanings that 'democracy' has, and, on the other hand, the consequences of the shift towards more political participation, including the functions media and journalism can and should fulfil to enable and foster participation in democracy. In doing so, WP2 provides the theoretical foundation for research in all other work packages. This applies particularly to WP6, which is using a Participatory Action Research approach, requiring permanent interaction between reflection (and theory-building) and action.

Considering the given resources, the following **organisational strategy** will be applied for to complete the **four tasks** of WP2, which will result in **four deliverables**:

T2.1 - Theoretical framework on democracy, participation and representation [M1-6]

Description:	A theoretical framework on democracy and its meanings prevalent in European societies will be developed that serves as a background for the review of various forms of political participation and the definition of the corresponding functions of the media.
Workplan:	Building a CU team
Deliverable:	D2.1 - Theoretical framework on democracy, participation and representation [M6]

T2.2 - Analytical models for examining media supply and demand side [M7-12]

Description:	The review of various forms of democratic political participation and the definition of the corresponding functions of the media will be used as a foundation for the analytical models used in WP3, WP4 and WP5.
Workplan:	Support from OEAW, IULM and JU, with a focus on T2.2 and second priority given to T2.3
Deliverable:	D2.2 - Analytical models for examining media supply and demand side [M12]

T2.3 - Theory-driven re-analysis of existing empirical data [M7-12]

Description:	Based on the theoretical framework on democracy, participation and representation (as developed in T2.1), a re-analysis of existing empirical data will allow for an empirical enrichment of the theoretical framework and for a theory-driven understanding of how democracy is perceived and practiced in the European Union.
Workplan:	Support from OEAW, IULM and JU, with a focus on T2.2 and second priority given to T2.3
Deliverable:	D2.3 - Results of the theory-driven reanalysis of existing empirical data [M18]

T2.4 - Continuous theory-driven re-analysis of the project's interventions [M13-36]

Description:	Work on theory will not stop throughout the project work: Democratic theory will serve as reference point for all analyses of the European political information environments carried out in WP3, WP4 and WP5. This will be realised through a set of internal workshops and reflection moments. The need for reflection applies particularly to the Participatory Action Research approach applied in WP6, which combines action and reflection.
Workplan:	Working with COMMIT
Deliverable:	D2.4 - Theory-driven re-analysis of the project's interventions [M36]

2.2.3 Work Package 3: Legal and (Self-)Regulatory Framework

WP title:	Legal and (self-)regulatory framework									
WP No.	3									
Lead beneficiary	OEAW									
Work package leader	Josef Seethaler									
Start month	1									
End month	20									
Participant number:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name participant:	OEAW	CU	IULM	JU	COMMIT	Lusófona Uni	TLU	IMT	MIC	MI
PM per participant:	12.00	2.00	2.00	6.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Tasks/participant	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2

Objectives: WP3 will provide an analysis of the legal provisions, regulatory standards and self-regulatory mechanisms, under which media operate, journalists work (= supply side) and people seek to meet their everyday life information and communication needs (= demand side). The main question is whether, in view of the current radical changes in media supply and use, the existing (mostly) representative approaches are being intensified, or whether participatory approaches are increasingly being adopted. At the EC level, policy initiatives such as the Whistleblower Directive, the Digital Service Act and the Media Freedom Act may indicate “an incremental shift in how democracy is perceived in Europe” (Keibel et al., 2021).

Since WP3 provides the context for the analysis and interpretation of the research in WP4 and WP5, it runs only in months 1-20. The work is split into **two tasks** that build on two different, complementary types of sources and different methodological approaches, and seek to achieve **three deliverables**:

T3.1 - Mapping legal and (self-)regulatory frameworks in the European Union [M1-12]

RQ:	How can the status quo of the legal framework, regulatory standards and self-regulatory mechanisms in EU Member States be described and characterized in terms of democratic standards?
Method:	Systematic review of international data collections, studies and documentary materials, supplemented by information from national sources
Workplan:	Mainly carried out by the WP leader in cooperation with JU (feedback and comments). If necessary, specific information requests will be made to partners, who should then consult legal texts, reports and databases on a national level. It can be assumed that not much additional information will be needed.
Deliverable:	D3.1 - Data set for the map of legal and (self-)regulatory frameworks for media in the European Union [M12]

T3.2 - Assessing legal and (self-)regulatory frameworks in EU countries [M10-20]

RQ:	Do the legal and (self-)regulatory frameworks in the ten Consortium countries reflect the current changes in the perception of democracy in Europe?
Method:	Semi-structured guideline interviews with leading representatives from regulatory authorities and self-regulatory bodies; qualitative content analysis
Workplan:	<p>(1) All partners: Semi-structured guideline interviews with at least one leading representative each from the national regulatory authority, a self-regulatory body and an audience organisation (“bottom-up perspective”); the questionnaire will be provided). Transcription of interviews, translation to English and identification of key statements. (The interviewees are not only of interest because of their exclusive knowledge, but because they shape the actions of other actors with their interpretations due to their position.)</p> <p>(2) Mainly carried out by the WP leader in cooperation with JU (feedback and comments): Comparative assessment of legal and (self-)regulatory frameworks for media in the European Union based on data from both tasks. The analysis is basis for the planned guidelines on how policymaking and self-regulation can contribute to a reinvigorated democracy through the media.</p>
Deliverables:	<p>D3.2 - Legal and (self-)regulatory frameworks in ten European countries [M16]</p> <p>D3.3 - Comparative assessment of legal and (self-)regulatory frameworks for media in Europe [M20]</p>

2.2.4 Work Package 4: The Supply Side

WP title:	The supply side									
WP No.	4									
Lead beneficiary	JU									
Work package leader	Beata Klimkiewicz									
Start month	1									
End month	36									
Participant number:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name participant:	OEAW	CU	IULM	JU	COMMIT	Lusófona Uni	TLU	IMT	MIC	MI
PM per participant:	2.00	2.00	5.00	27.00	2.00	10.00	10.00	11.00	5.00	5.00
Tasks/participant	1-4	1-4	1-4	1-4	1-4	1-4	1-4	1-4	1-4	1-4

Objectives: WP4 aims to provide a detailed picture of media supply throughout the European Union, encompassing the entire spectrum of news media, across all channels, mandates and

sources of financing side, and the media's potential to promote and support different forms of political participation.

Like WP3 and WP5, WP 4 is organized in **two strands**: a wide-scale quantitative inquiry, based on secondary data and realized at the European level; and an in-depth analysis of media production that will be carried out in the ten countries represented in the Consortium. The two strands will be pursued within **four tasks**, which will result in **seven deliverables**. The **contribution of partners** to each task depends on the number of their PMs.

T4.1 - Mapping media in the European Union [M1-12]

RQ:	What is the composition and structure of the political information environments in the EU countries, encompassing the entire spectrum of news media, across all channels, mandates and sources of financing?
Method:	<p>Collection and analysis of secondary data on</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> media outlets (variables: reach, geographical distribution [national, regional, local], source of funding [advertising, subscription, state, subsidies, grants, user donations], mandate [PSM, commercial, non-profit], ownership, political orientation [?]) and media structures (media concentration [advertising and audience market], platform concentration [advertising], ownership and transparency [description of ownership groups]) <p>(final lists of variables will be provided)</p>
Workplan:	<p>Work schedule:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> June 1, 2023: Operationalisation of variables and setting media outlets samples July 15, 2023: Developing templates for country outputs November 15, 2023: Country outputs December 1, 2023: Collection and analysis of secondary data February 2024: Completing D4.2 <p>Distribution of PMs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimal involvement: 2 PM - OEAW, CU, COMMITT = 0,5 PM for country outputs Medium involvement: 5 PM - IULM, MIC = 0,5 PM for country reports High involvement: 10 PM - Lusofona = 3 PM, TLU = 2 PM; 11 PM -IMT = 3 PM <p>All partners are invited to contribute throughout the project to the already established "MeDeMAP Media Blog" (D4.1).</p>
Deliverable:	<p>D4.1 - Media mapping blog [M1]</p> <p>D4.2 - Data set for the map of EU media systems [M12]</p>

T4.2 - Assessing media production in ten EU countries [M13-24]

RQ:	What is the composition and structure of the political information environments in the EU countries, encompassing the entire spectrum of news media, across all channels, mandates and sources of financing?
Method:	Interviews with representatives of media regulatory authorities, industry and journalists (variables related to production conditions and business models, reflecting in principle conditions for <i>good practices</i> and <i>limitations</i> ; questionnaire will be provided)
Workplan:	12 interviews: Interviews with 2 representatives from each of 6 types of media outlets Partners transcribe and translate answers into English
Deliverables:	D4.3 - Media production in ten European countries [M22] D4.4 - Comparative assessment of media supply and production in ten EU countries [M24]

T4.3 - Assessing political participation through and in the media [M21-32]

RQ:	What is the media's potential for promoting and supporting various forms of political participation?
Method:	Survey (CAWI) among media managers, journalists, social media channel managers (variables = options for political participation through the media and in the media, focusing on <i>good practices</i> ; questionnaire will be provided)
Workplan:	2 PM partners: only closed-ended questions 5 PM partners and more: closed-ended and open-ended questions; partners transcribe and translate answers into English
Deliverables:	D4.5 - Political participation through and in the media in ten European countries [M30] D4.6 - Comparative assessment of political participation through and in the media in EU countries [M32]

T4.4 - Final analysis: Media and democracy [M28-36]

RQ:	What is the composition and structure of the political information environments in the EU countries, encompassing the entire spectrum of news media, across all channels, mandates and sources of financing? What is the media's potential for promoting and supporting various forms of political participation?
Method:	Summarising the main conceptual issues and empirical results
Workplan:	All partners provide support (around 0.5 PM)
Deliverable:	D4.7 - Report on media and democracy in the European Union [M36]

The leader of WP4 established a “Defining Media” task force, which has the task of discussing the definition of ‘media’ and deciding what types of media should be included into the analysis.

2.2.5 Work Package 5: The Demand Side

WP title:	The demand side									
WP No.	5									
Lead beneficiary	IULM									
Work package leader	Andrea Miconi									
Start month	1									
End month	36									
Participant number:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name participant:	OEAW	CU	IULM	JU	COMMIT	Lusófona Uni	TLU	IMT	MIC	MI
PM per participant:	2.00	2.00	25.00	2.00	2.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	5.00	5.00
Tasks/participant	1-4	2-4	1-4	3-4	3-4	3-4	3-4	3-4	3-4	3-4

Objectives: WP5 will provide an advanced knowledge of the demand side: public perception of the connection between media and democracy; trust and distrust in media and democratic institutions; possible implications of audience practices in terms of social agency and political participation. The goal of WP5 is to analyse “the amount and quality of information that people are interested in –or to be more precise: how and why various segments within a society make use of news information available through traditional and new digital media”.

For this goal, we will work on **two main dimensions**:

- (1) The media repertoires people choose to meet their information needs [with a “holistic repertoire-oriented approach”],
- (2) the reasons and motives for this selection, and, in particular, the democratic attitudes and expectations associated with it.

These two dimensions are translated into **four research questions**:

- (RQ1) How democratic notions and expectations towards democratic functions of the media are distributed among a country’s population and the extent to which they strengthen trust in the media;
- (RQ2) how trust in the media is related to trust in democracy and democratic institutions;
- (RQ3) how the media repertoires of the various audience groups maintaining certain democratic notions are composed;
- (RQ4) how the members of the groups can be described in terms of socio-demographic characteristics.

The four research questions will be pursued within **four tasks**, using **different methods** and resulting in **six deliverables**:

T5.1 - A map of audience evolution in the European Union [M1-12]

RQ:	RQ3, RQ4
Method:	Analysis of secondary data on the state of European audiences (variables: media use)
Workplan:	<p>(1) IULM shares with OEAW a list of sources to be used, and a more readable report on the data that we have collected for the EUMEPLAT project Deadline: M3 [May 31, 2023]</p> <p>(2) Feedback from OEAW and definition of the sources and guidelines Deadline: M4 [June 30, 2023]</p> <p>(3) Data collection realized by IULM Deadline: M10 [December 31, 2023]</p> <p>(4) Data compilation and drawing of the report by IULM Deadline: M12 [February 29, 2024]</p> <p>Time effort: 90% IULM; 10% OEAW</p>
Deliverables:	D5.1 - Dataset for the map of European audiences [M12]

T5.2 - Assessing trust in media and democratic institutions [M1-14]

RQ:	RQ2, RQ3
Method:	Analysis of secondary data about people's trust in news media and democratic institutions (variables: media attitudes; media use; political attitude; political participation)
Workplan:	<p>(1) IULM shares with OEAW and CU a list of sources to be used, and a more readable report on the data that we have collected for the EUMEPLAT project Deadline: M4 [June 30, 2023]</p> <p>(2) Feedback from OEAW and CU and definition of the sources and guidelines Deadline: M7 [September 30, 2023]</p> <p>(3) Data collection realized by IULM Deadline: M11 [January 31, 2024]</p> <p>(4) Aggregated analysis and drawing of the report by IULM Deadline: M14 [April 30, 2024]</p> <p>Time effort: 80% IULM; 10% OEAW; 10% CU</p>
Deliverables:	D5.2 - Report on trust and democratic institutions in Europe [M14]

T5.3 - Ethnographic inquiry on media practices in ten European countries [M12-26]

RQ:	RQ2, RQ3
Method:	Ethnographic sessions realized in each country (variables: media attitudes; media use; political attitude; political participation)
Workplan:	<p>(1) Draft version of the methodological guidelines released by IULM (M12-16) at M14</p> <p>(2) Qualitative analysis and translation (M15-20): We are expected to interview at least 40 people per country, for a minimum number of 400, but the staff effort is unbalanced. A proposal:</p>

- OEAW [2 P/M]: 4 focus groups, 32 interviewees (Germany)
- CU [2 P/M]: 4 focus groups, 32 interviewees
- IULM [25 P/M]: 40 interviews and 4 focus groups, 72 interviewees
- JU [2 P/M]: 4 focus groups, 32 interviewees
- COMMIT [2 P/M]: 4 focus groups, 32 interviewees (Austria)
- Lusófona Uni [10 P/M]: 10 interviews and 4 focus groups, 42 interviewees
- TLU [10 P/M]: 10 interviews and 4 focus groups, 42 interviewees
- IMT [10 P/M]: 10 interviews and 4 focus groups, 42 interviewees
- MIC [5 P/M]: 5 focus groups, 48 interviewees
- MI [2 P/M]: 4 focus groups, 32 interviewees
- Total: 406 interviewees

(3) Analysis and drawing of the report by IULM [M21-24]

Deliverables: D5.3 - Methodological protocol for ethnographic research [M16]
 D5.4 - Audience's media practices in ten European countries [national reports] [M24]
 D5.5 - Report on audience needs in ten EU countries (aggregated analysis) [M26]

T5.4 - Multi-dimensional clustering: People, media and democracy [M24-36]

RQ:	RQ3, RQ4
Method:	Synoptic analysis of the ten ethnographic sessions [400 cases at least]; LCA (or similar) analysis of quantitative data
Workplan:	-
Deliverables:	D5.6 - People, media and democracy: a quali-quantitative assessment [M36]

The WP leader proposed the establishment of an “Aggregated Data Analysis” task force. (For the organization of task forces, see Chapter 1.3.)

2.2.6 Work Package 6: Supply Meets Demand

WP title:	Supply meets demand									
WP No.	6									
Lead beneficiary	COMMIT									
Work package leader	Helmut Peissl									
Start month	17									
End month	36									
Participant number:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name participant:	OEAW	CU	IULM	JU	COMMIT	Lusófona Uni	TLU	IMT	MIC	MI
PM per participant:	2.00	9.00	4.00	2.00	16.00	2.00			7.00	7.00
Tasks/participant	1-4	1-4	1-4	1	1-4	2			1-4	1-4

Objectives: The objective of WP6 is to realise dialogical interactions of citizens and media stakeholders meeting in citizens' parliaments to contribute for the development of the future media map. The conceptualization of the process will be based on results of WP 3,4,5. The final concept and moderation of the process will be based on best practise research on successful practise of policy development with citizens' parliaments in Europe.

WP6 activities will start formally in month 17. It consists of **four tasks**, which will result in **five deliverables**:

T6.1 - Methodological report on successful practice of policy development with citizens' parliaments in Europe (M 17-22)

RQ:	What are good practice examples of citizens' parliaments and applications of the Participatory Action Research (PAR) approach?
Method:	Desk research: Analysis of successful practice of policy development with citizens' parliaments and successful applications of the Participatory Action Research (PAR) approach. This will also include research on specific and productive methods of moderation, e.g., "Art of Hosting".
Workplan:	WP leader handles these tasks, and partners provide some support (e.g., literature references, knowledge about successful events)
Deliverables:	D6.1- Research report on successful practice of policy development with citizens' parliaments in Europe (M22)

T6.2 - Implementation of citizens' parliaments in local contexts of the countries covered (M 23-30)

RQ:	How to conceptualize and organize a citizens' parliament?
Method:	Participatory Action Research (PAR)
Workplan:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The design of the citizens' parliaments will be developed by the WP leader in cooperation with leader of WP2 (CU). (b) WP leader provides detailed guidelines for implementing a citizens' parliament. (c) In Austria and Germany, the citizens' parliaments will be organized by the WP leader with support of OEAW. WP leader is responsible for the minutes. (d) In selected countries, the respective partners will organize the citizens' parliaments. They are responsible for the minutes and the translation of the minutes and resolutions. (e) Each partner is expected to contribute at least one blog post.
Deliverables:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D6.2 - Design of citizens' parliaments (M24) D6.3 - Blog on citizens' parliaments (M25-30)

T6.3 - Analysis of the sessions and final decisions of citizens' parliaments (M 26-36)

RQ:	What are the results of the citizens' parliaments?
Method:	Analysis of the results of the citizens' parliaments based on the session minutes and resolutions and according to the analytical concepts developed in WP2.
Workplan:	Analysis is handled by the WP leader.
Deliverables:	D6.4 - Report "Future roadmap for European media and democracy" (M32)

T6.4 - Evaluation of PAR research (M 31-36)

RQ:	What can be learned from the conceptualization and the results of the citizens' parliaments?
Method:	Reflecting participatory practices that may serve as blueprints for the future of accessible media production and programming.
Workplan:	As the Participatory Action Research approach requires permanent interaction between reflection (and theory-building) and action, Task 6.4 will be carried out by the WP leader with support of the leader of WP2 (CU).
Deliverables:	D6.5 - Leaflets and online guidance on participatory media practices (M36)

2.2.7 Work Package 7: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

WP title:	Dissemination, exploitation and communication									
WP No.	7									
Lead beneficiary	Lusófona Uni									
Work package leader	Manuel José Damásio									
Start month	1									
End month	36									
Participant number:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Short name participant:	OEAW	CU	IULM	JU	COMMIT	Lusófona Uni	TLU	IMT	MIC	MI
PM per participant:	10.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	28.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Tasks/participant	2-4	2-4	2-4	2-4	2-4	1-4	2-4	2-4	2-4	2-4

Objectives: The objective of this WP is to reach, inform, involve, engage and activate a large range of target groups in different regions and to ensure the reach (or surpass) of the expected impacts for each project activity. The WP involves all partners in valorizing each action and reaching out to their regional networks to guarantee a large participation in all activities, promoting activities and results according to the different audiences/target groups, and ensuring an appropriate and timely implementation of the various dissemination channels and means (local and international). Gender balance will be taken into account when involving stakeholders, communication tools will be checked in order to make them inclusive for all and overcome gender blindness. Special attention will be given to the relation between

dissemination and exploitation of main deliverables in particular the relevance they can have for specific targets – NGOs and students per example.

WP7 aims & goals:

- To address multiple audiences that are present across the relationships between media, politics and the public.
- Focus on participatory democracy, including measures to empower people to voice their own concerns, opinions, and points of view.
- Map of the European media landscape and related outputs - key dissemination elements.

On April 27, 2023, the [MeDeMAP Website](https://www.medemap.eu/) (<https://www.medemap.eu/>) went online. The website is the main information resource for stakeholders and all interested in the project. It will present important project results including the already established “[MeDeMAP Media Blog](#)” (D4.1). The MeDeMAP brand kit (including the MeDeMAP Graphic Standards Manual) is available on the MeDeMAP MS Teams site (see Chapter 5). The final Dissemination & Exploitation Plan was provided in month 6.

Draft communication plan:

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Description</i>
Visual identity	Definition of a consistent image of the project across different channels.
Communication & Dissemination materials	Printed and digital materials (editable format to enable translation to local languages).
Website, Platform & Blog	Project information & results. Map of the European political information environments. “MeDeMAP Media Blog” - regular updates on research (short texts) - one central blog for all WPs . Linked with website.
Newsletter	Semi-annual e-newsletter . Coordinated by U Lusófona. Authored by different partners. Project news and resources. Special attention to targeted e-mailings.
Social media channels & Podcast	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn, Telegram + YouTube (video docs). Podcast: Anchor (creation + hosting + distribution). Short news of the project, new project publications, other related activities. Partners (particularly regional coordinators) will work with local stakeholders to produce material for social media (short digital videos/ podcasts) - empower them to tell their story.
Traditional media	National press releases on the occasion of significant milestones (each partner).
Project events	Impact workshops/ project meetings/ internal workshops .

External workshops, conferences/events, scientific and non-scientific publications	Minimum of two presentations at external events (each partner). Publish findings and insights in scientific and non-scientific publications . Special focus on Open Access journals .
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Target</i>
Website & Platform	NGOs in the countries studied by the Project/ Regulators and self-regulation organisations/ Media practitioners/ Academics & researchers/ HE students/ General public
Newsletter	NGOs in the countries studied by the Project/ Regulators and self-regulation organisations/ Media practitioners/ Academics & researchers
Social media channels	NGOs in the countries studied by the Project/ Regulators and self-regulation organisations/ Media practitioners/ Academics & researchers/ HE students/ General public
Traditional media	NGOs in the countries studied by the Project/ Regulators and self-regulation organisations/ Media practitioners
Short digital videos / podcasts	NGOs in the countries studied by the Project/ Media practitioners/ Students/ Educational sector
Events / workshops	NGOs in the countries studied by the Project/ Regulators and self-regulation organisations/ Media practitioners/ Academics & researchers/ HE students
Non-scientific events and publications	NGOs in the countries studied by the Project/ Regulators and self-regulation organisations/ Media practitioners/ Educational sector

Dissemination plan:

Main objectives:

1. **Raise awareness on MeDeMAP** and its approach to political information environments by providing an **integrated, solid and appealing image** for **target groups** using **appropriate channels and messages**.
2. **Ensure visibility for project's actions, activities and results** making sure to **connect to the relevant EU initiatives** (for example, the Media Pluralism Monitor, developed by the Centre for Media Pluralism and Media Freedom at the EUI, and the new European Media Ownership Monitor, developed by the Euromedia Group) and **European and international organizations** (ECPMF, ERGA, AIPCE, EFJ, RSF, EBU, CMFE among many others).
3. **Promote ownership of results** with the main **target groups** by applying **co-creation and direct engagement of citizens**.

4. **Exploit and promote adoption of the model for quali-quantitative data collection and analysis, promoting a new approach to understanding news media and their affordances.**
5. **Contribute to shaping the European and scientific dialogue on news media by becoming a point of reference.**

Main relevant stakeholders:

- **NGOs active in political participation, civic engagement and media literacy, both internationally and in the countries studied by the Project.**
- **regulators and self-regulation organizations.**
- **media practitioners (addressed via media associations and journalists' organizations).**

Main message of the project:

- **RESEARCH-BASED APPROACHES TO MEDIA DEMOCRATIZATION ARE POSSIBLE AND NECESSARY**

Exploitation plan – general activities:

1. **Policy papers** for different stakeholders.
2. **Leaflets and online guidance on how media and information literacy can be improved, and media content creation can be put in the hands of communities and citizens.**
3. **Workshops on using the map of European political information environments as a decision-making tool.**
4. **Roadshows – presenting the map and key stories.**
5. **Production of podcasts and filmic stories of participation.**

Internal communications:

Microsoft Teams is a complete corporate collaboration hub that will allow responding to all communication needs that will arise within the project - making available and sharing files, organising meetings, creating dedicated channels for specific tasks and WPs, etc.

MeDeMAP MS Teams structure:

3 Deliverables and Standards

3.1 General Overview of the Deliverables

Each document deliverable in the MeDeMAP's project will be assigned a specific document number (in accordance with the number of the deliverable). Any updates made to the documents must be shared on MeDeMAP's Microsoft Teams site, while previous versions must be stored in a separate folder named "Archive". Table 3 provides a summary of all the relevant information on MeDeMAP's deliverables, including the leading participant, the document type, the dissemination level, and the deadline for each deliverable. On the other hand, Table 4 lists the deliverables by their due submission dates, and Table 5 shows which milestones develop from them.

Table 3

Deliverables by Work Package Responsible for Delivery

No	Deliverable Name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Level	Due Date
D1.1	Coordination plan	WP1	OEAW	Other	Public	30.04.2023
D1.2	Data management plan	WP1	OEAW	DMP	Public	31.08.2023
D1.3	Completion of quantitative data input for the map of European political information environments	WP1	OEAW	Data sets etc	Sensitive	31.05.2024
D1.4	Completion of the front end of the map	WP1	OEAW	Websites etc	Public	31.08.2024
D1.5	Periodic report I	WP1	OEAW	Document, report	Public	30.04.2024
D1.6	Completion of input of data from qualitative research for the map of European political information environments	WP1	OEAW	Datasets etc	Public	31.10.2025
D1.7	Policy papers for different stakeholders	WP1	OEAW	Document, report	Public	28.02.2026
D1.8	Periodic report II & Final report (60 days after end of the reporting period)	WP1	OEAW	Document, report	Public	28.02.2026
D2.1	Theoretical framework on democracy, participation and representation	WP2	CU	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	Public	31.08.2023
D2.2	Analytical models for examining supply and demand side	WP2	CU	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	Public	29.02.2024
D2.3	Results of the theory-driven re-analysis of existing empirical data	WP2	CU	Document, report	Public	31.08.2024
D2.4	Theory-driven re-analysis of the project's interventions	WP2	CU	Document, report	Public	28.02.2026
D3.1	Data set for the map of legal and (self-)regulatory frameworks for media in the EU	WP3	OEAW	Datasets etc	Sensitive	29.02.2024

No	Deliverable Name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Level	Due Date
D3.2	Legal and (self-) regulatory frameworks in ten European countries - Country reports	WP3	OEAW	Document, report	Public	30.06.2024
D3.3	Comparative assessment of legal and (self-) regulatory frameworks for media in Europe	WP3	OEAW	Document, report	Public	31.10.2024
D4.1	Media mapping blog	WP4	JU	Websites etc	Public	31.03.2023
D4.2	Data set for the map of EU media systems	WP4	JU	Datasets etc	Sensitive	29.02.2024
D4.3	Media production in ten European countries WP4 - Country reports	WP4	JU	Document, report	Public	31.12.2024
D4.4	Comparative assessment of media supply and production in ten EU countries	WP4	JU	Document, report	Public	28.02.2025
D4.5	Political participation through and in the media in ten European countries - Country reports	WP4	JU	Document, report	Public	31.08.2025
D4.6	Comparative assessment of political participation through and in the media in EU countries	WP4	JU	Document, report	Public	31.10.2025
D4.7	Report on media and democracy in the European Union	WP4	JU	Document, report	Public	28.02.2026
D5.1	Data set for the map of European audiences	WP5	IULM	Datasets etc	Sensitive	29.02.2024
D5.2	Report on trust in media and democratic institutions in Europe	WP5	IULM	Document, report	Public	30.04.2024
D5.3	Methodological protocol for ethnographic research	WP5	IULM	Other	Public	30.06.2024
D5.4	Audiences' media practices in ten European countries - Country reports	WP5	IULM	Document, report	Public	28.02.2025
D5.5	Comparative report on audience needs in ten EU countries	WP5	IULM	Document, report	Public	30.04.2025
D5.6	People, media and democracy: a quali-quantitative assessment	WP5	IULM	Document, report	Public	28.02.2026
D6.1	Research report on successful practise of policy development with citizens' parliaments in Europe	WP6	COMMIT	Document, report	Public	31.12.2024
D6.2	Design of citizens' parliaments	WP6	COMMIT	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	Public	28.02.2025
D6.3	Blog on citizens' parliaments	WP6	COMMIT	Websites etc	Public	31.08.2025
D6.4	Report "Future roadmap for European media and democracy"	WP6	COMMIT	Document, report	Public	31.10.2025
D6.5	Leaflets and online guidance on participatory media practices	WP6	COMMIT	Document, report	Public	28.02.2026
D7.1	Website and project logo	WP7	Lusófona Uni	Websites etc	Public	30.04.2023
D7.2	Dissemination and exploitation plan	WP7	Lusófona Uni	Other	Public	31.08.2023
D7.3	Project meetings and impact workshops	WP7	Lusófona Uni	Other	Public	28.02.2026

Table 4
Deliverables by Date of Due Submission

No	Deliverable Name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Level	Due Date
D4.1	Media mapping blog	WP4	JU	Websites etc	Public	31.03.2023
D1.1	Coordination plan	WP1	OEAW	Other	Public	30.04.2023
D7.1	Website and project logo	WP7	Lusófona Uni	Websites etc	Public	30.04.2023
D1.2	Data management plan	WP1	OEAW	DMP	Public	31.08.2023
D2.1	Theoretical framework on democracy, participation and representation	WP2	CU	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	Public	31.08.2023
D7.2	Dissemination and exploitation plan	WP7	Lusófona Uni	Other	Public	31.08.2023
D2.2	Analytical models for examining supply and demand side	WP2	CU	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	Public	29.02.2024
D3.1	Data set for the map of legal and (self-)regulatory frameworks for media in the EU	WP3	OEAW	Datasets etc	Sensitive	29.02.2024
D4.2	Data set for the map of EU media systems	WP4	JU	Datasets etc	Sensitive	29.02.2024
D5.1	Data set for the map of European audiences	WP5	IULM	Datasets etc	Sensitive	29.02.2024
D5.2	Report on trust in media and democratic institutions in Europe	WP5	IULM	Document, report	Public	30.04.2024
D1.5	Periodic report I	WP1	OEAW	Document, report	Public	30.04.2024
D1.3	Completion of quantitative data input for the map of European political information environments	WP1	OEAW	Datasets etc	Sensitive	31.05.2024
D3.2	Legal and (self-) regulatory frameworks in ten European countries - Country reports	WP3	OEAW	Document, report	Public	30.06.2024
D5.3	Methodological protocol for ethnographic research	WP5	IULM	Other	Public	30.06.2024
D1.4	Completion of the front end of the map	WP1	OEAW	Websites etc	Public	31.08.2024
D2.3	Results of the theory-driven re-analysis of existing empirical data	WP2	CU	Document, report	Public	31.08.2024
D3.3	Comparative assessment of legal and (self-) regulatory frameworks for media in Europe	WP3	OEAW	Document, report	Public	31.10.2024
D4.3	Media production in ten European countries WP4 - Country reports	WP4	JU	Document, report	Public	31.12.2024
D6.1	Research report on successful practise of policy development with citizens' parliaments in Europe	WP6	COMMIT	Document, report	Public	31.12.2024
D4.4	Comparative assessment of media supply and production in ten EU countries	WP4	JU	Document, report	Public	28.02.2025

No	Deliverable Name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Level	Due Date
D5.4	Audiences' media practices in ten European countries - Country reports	WP5	IULM	Document, report	Public	28.02.2025
D6.2	Design of citizens' parliaments	WP6	COMMIT	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	Public	28.02.2025
D5.5	Comparative report on audience needs in ten EU countries	WP5	IULM	Document, report	Public	30.04.2025
D4.5	Political participation through and in the media in ten European countries - Country reports	WP4	JU	Document, report	Public	31.08.2025
D6.3	Blog on citizens' parliaments	WP6	COMMIT	Websites etc	Public	31.08.2025
D1.6	Completion of input of data from qualitative research for the map of European political information environments	WP1	OEAW	Datasets etc	Public	31.10.2025
D4.6	Comparative assessment of political participation through and in the media in EU countries	WP4	JU	Document, report	Public	31.10.2025
D6.4	Report "Future roadmap for European media and democracy"	WP6	COMMIT	Document, report	Public	31.10.2025
D1.7	Policy papers for different stakeholders	WP1	OEAW	Document, report	Public	28.02.2026
D1.8	Periodic report II & Final report (60 days after end of the reporting period)	WP1	OEAW	Document, report	Public	28.02.2026
D2.4	Theory-driven re-analysis of the project's interventions	WP2	CU	Document, report	Public	28.02.2026
D4.7	Report on media and democracy in the European Union	WP4	JU	Document, report	Public	28.02.2026
D5.6	People, media and democracy: a qualitative assessment	WP5	IULM	Document, report	Public	28.02.2026
D6.5	Leaflets and online guidance on participatory media practices	WP6	COMMIT	Document, report	Public	28.02.2026
D7.3	Project meetings and impact workshops	WP7	Lusófona Uni	OTHER	Public	28.02.2026

Table 5
List of MeDeMAP Milestones

Milestone number	Milestone name	Related WP	Due date (month)	Means of verification
1	Team building	WP6, WP7, WP5, WP4, WP3, WP1, WP2	3	Communication structure is established; all partners are familiar with objectives, schedule, and management structure.
2	Visibility	WP7	6	Project website published.
3	Theoretical foundation	WP2	12	Analytical models for WP4 and 5 provided.

Milestone number	Milestone name	Related WP	Due date (month)	Means of verification
4	Completion of quantitative data collection	WP5, WP4, WP3, WP1	12	Data sets are provided.
5	Completion of front-end of the EU media map	WP7, WP1	18	EU media map available on the website.
6	First qualitative analyses	WP5, WP4, WP3, WP1	26	Reports available and discussed in project meetings.
7	Completion of qualitative data input into map	WP7, WP1	32	Revised EU media map available on the website.
8	Report on results of citizens' parliaments	WP6	32	Report available.
9	Final reports and assessments & Overall final report	WP7, WP6, WP5, WP4, WP3, WP2, WP1	36	Reports available.
10	Policy papers	WP6, WP5, WP4, WP3, WP1	36	Papers available and distributed to stakeholders.

3.2 Deliverable Submission Process

Deliverables must use the template for reports that will be available on the MeDeMAP's Microsoft Teams site. Scientific citations in deliverables must follow the APA citation standard, 7th edition (see, for example: <https://owl.massey.ac.nz/referencing/apa-interactive.php>; https://owl.purdue.edu/owl/research_and_citation/apa_style/apa_formatting_and_style_guide/index.html). An executive summary should be included as part of each deliverable.

WP leaders are responsible for monitoring the progress and due dates of the deliverables (see Table 4). In case of a delay, the Coordinator must be informed in advance with good time to take action. The Coordinator will in turn inform the Project Officer.

The partner(s) in charge of the deliverable will work closely with the respective WP leader. 37 days before the deadline they will receive a notification by the Coordinator. The WP leader will have maximum 7 days to share a first version of the deliverable with the Steering Committee. Steering Committee members will have 14 days to provide feedback on this version (see Chapter 3.3). The partner(s) in charge of the deliverable and the WP leader will have 10 days to revise the first version and upload the final version of the deliverable to MeDeMAP's Microsoft Teams site, to be accepted by the Coordinator (in accordance with the Grant Agreement). In case of acceptance, the Coordinator will upload and submit the final version of deliverable to the Funding & Tenders Portal and notify project partners about the submission and availability of the final deliverable in MS Teams. In case of rejection, the Coordinator will ask the WP leader to revise the deliverable again and/or seek a second opinion from the Steering Committee.

3.3 Quality Assurance

The purpose of the quality assurance procedure is to safeguard the quality of the **scientific documents and reports**, in terms of (1.) format and style, and (2.) scientific standards and consistency.

Task 7.2 (Communication artefacts), lead by Lusófona University, will define the format and style for MeDeMAP's documents.

In order to ensure the quality of the content of scientific documents and reports, the authoring party or person of a deliverable shall share it with the Steering Committee, which shall provide feedback. In terms of consistency, special attention will be given to the coherent and consistent use of key terms. WP leaders are still responsible for the quality of the deliverables; however, the Steering Committee must review them to approve for submission. The project coordinator shall collect the feedback and communicate it to the author(s) on the next day after receiving all feedback.

Procedures for information and documentation management are further specified and elaborated in D7.2 (Dissemination and exploitation plan).

4 Meetings

4.1 Meetings within the Consortium

Throughout the project, meetings are held at various levels:

- Meetings of the General Assembly
- Meetings of the Steering Committee
- Work Package meetings
- Task Force meetings

In its meeting of March 9, 2023, the General Assembly unanimously agreed that the General Assembly meetings should take place twice a year. Meetings should take place in March and September. 3rd week of September for 2024 and 2025 would be preferable. The WP leaders are encouraged to host these meetings. The host partner is responsible for establishing the agenda of the meeting (with the approval of the Coordinator and the contribution of the other members).

It is advisable to combine the meetings of the General Assembly with meetings of the Steering Committee (which will be organized by the Coordinator) and WP meetings (which will be organized by WP leaders).

Eventual interim SC meetings and WP meetings should preferably be held online. This also applies to any task force meetings that may be required. Meetings of Task Forces will be organized by the respective leader.

Information on convening meetings of the General Assembly and the Steering Committee are described in the Consortium Agreement.

Regarding the organization of WP meetings, the General Assembly unanimously approved the following procedure: WP leaders are recommended to convene WP meetings (in-person, virtual or hybrid) at crucial stages of the research to discuss the details of the upcoming tasks. It is up to the WP leader to decide on when and how to have such a meeting, and the leaders of all invited partners decide who will be delegated from the respective team. In advance of these meetings, the WP leader should provide written guidelines for the task at hand so that the meeting can focus on finetuning the guidelines.

4.2 Meetings outside the Consortium

Other meetings include two impact workshops with relevant stakeholders at the beginning and at the end of the project to discuss the aims as well as preliminary results of the research with European experts, in particular from regulators, press councils, media associations and journalists' organizations but also from the scientific community for building momentum. In addition, further workshops within the consortium could be organized, to which significant stakeholders can also be invited. However, these workshops and invitations should be coordinated by the leader of WP7 "Dissemination, exploitation and communication".

MeDeMAP is expected to organise a cluster event with the other two projects funded under the same topic:

1. Resilient media for democracy in the digital age (ReMeD), coordinated by the University of Navara in Spain, contact person: mmedina@unav.es
2. Fostering capacity building for civic resilience and participation: Dialogic communication ethics and accountability (DIACOMET), coordinated by the Vytautas Magnus University in Lithuania, contact person: egle.gerulaitiene@vdu.lt

The coordinator, WP leaders and other beneficiaries may be requested to participate in EU review meetings, including with outside experts who assist the granting authority.

5 Information and Documentation Management

MS Teams has been chosen as a tool for collaboration and control of project documents and information. Membership in the teams is organized according to the project's WP structure, thus ensuring day-to-day collaboration between and virtual meetings of the respective WP partners.

All scientific outputs (reports, papers, conference presentations, etc.) as well as the tools developed in the project are intellectual property of the involved partners but will be available to all project participants (with proper reference to the IPR holders). Deliverables and project publications, if open access, will be made available on the MeDeMAP website. The rules for intellectual property management are defined in the Consortium Agreement.

Internal communication will primarily take place via email. Separate mailing lists have been generated for the Steering Committee, the General Assembly and all researchers involved in MeDeMAP.

6 Risk Management and Conflict Resolution

6.1 Critical Risks

A limited number of risks are relevant to the project, which, in the worst case, might cause delay in achieving some of the milestones (see Table 6). There are two major problems:

1. How can validity of secondary data be provided despite different measurement methods?
2. How can functional equivalence of the measured constructs be ensured?

Ad 1. The collection of already available data, which is considered as so-called 'secondary data' with regard to new research objectives, is based on the review and analysis of published datasets and studies. This implies that secondary data research draws on data that was primarily collected for a different purpose, using a different method, on a different legal basis and by different people or institutions. While a comprehensive and well-informed research methodology can be achieved through the integration of primary and secondary research, particular emphasis must be placed on the evaluation and transparency of generation and transmission of secondary data. Three measures should be emphasised in particular:

- (a) *Evaluating the source.* The quality and availability of secondary data can vary depending on the characteristics of the source or provider alone. Researchers must critically assess the credibility, reliability and relevance of the source, but also clarify the legal basis for using the data before including it in their research.
- (b) *Conducting plausibility checks and checking logical consistency of the data.* Secondary data may contain inherent biases or limitations that may be due to the original definition, collection method or calculation mode. Moreover, the data may be outdated and may not take into account more recent information or developments.

In addition to simple plausibility and consistency checks to detect errors and typos, the definitions, data collection methods and calculation formulae (e.g. for indices or rankings) used in the various sources must be checked for appropriateness on the basis of the methodologies, codebooks or questionnaires provided. Data based on methods, codebooks or questionnaires that appear to be (even partially) inconsistent or non-transparent will not be included in any MeDeMAP dataset. A more reliable judgement on the plausibility of data can often only be made by comparison, i.e. by comparing data from one year with previous or subsequent years or by comparing data from different sources but based on similar definitions. The comparison of data from different sources will be facilitated by transforming all data so that they lie within the same range of values. Various ways of grouping data, e.g. according to theoretically or statistically derived criteria for certain thresholds, can also help to check the quality of the data.

- (c) *Documenting the data preparation.* Any documentation of datasets should contain a description of the transmitted data, the context in which it was created and the subsequent transformations up to the generation of the new dataset. Its purpose is twofold. On the one hand, it enables the user of the secondary data prepared under

new aspects to critically assess the data. On the other hand, it helps the researchers themselves: Since secondary data has been collected for different purposes, it may not perfectly match the specific research needs. The reflection that precedes the documentation allows the researchers to identify limitations in terms of variables, definitions or the granularity of the data.

Based on such a source-critical evaluation of secondary data, its use provides researchers with a broader understanding of the topic, enabling them to recognise gaps in existing knowledge and refine their research questions accordingly. Primary research methods such as surveys or expert interviews can then be conducted to collect new data that directly addresses these research gaps. The results of primary research can be compared and validated with the knowledge gained through secondary research. By combining the findings from both types of research, researchers can close knowledge gaps, increase the reliability of their findings and draw meaningful conclusions that contribute to the overall understanding of the topic.

Ad 2. The problem of functional equivalency, i.e. the problem of guaranteeing that functionally comparable elements are being measured in all countries, is well-known in cross-national research. To eliminate it, we use a multi-stage process of method development (check and re-check) in the potentially affected work packages, particularly WP3, WP4 and WP5, in which all partners were involved in checking terms and operationalisation options in the context of their countries and languages. We established an iterative process, where the translator understands the concept in the source language and finds a wording to express the same concept in the target language in a way in which the equivalent conveys the same meaning and intent as the original. 'Iterative process' means that we repeat this action of translation and re-translation to find the best possible solution. This makes it possible to develop research designs (mostly questionnaires) that can be used as a basis for country comparisons.

6.2 Conflict Resolution

As a general principle, any conflicts that cannot be resolved at one level or below may be resolved at a higher level in the project's governance structure. This means that conflicts within work packages should be resolved by the WP leader or if needed by the Coordinator or ultimately by the Consortium in a General Assembly (if needed, in an extraordinary GA). More information can be found in the Consortium Agreement which governs the settlement of internal conflicts.

7 Cost and Schedule Management

The objectives of cost and schedule management include planning the expenses and resources for the project, as well as the identification of possible deviations from planned costs and the time plan, and the proposal of corrective actions that will ensure that the project is completed within the given time and financial constraints. Timely and accurate reporting is a key part of the cost and schedule management. The Coordinator is responsible for reporting to the European Commission at the end of each reporting period (reporting period 1: month 1 – month 12, reporting period 2: month 13 to month 36). At MeDeMAP's kick-off meeting on March 9, 2023, the Project Officer provided guidelines for the periodic reports in general (Figure 5) and financial reporting in particular (Figure 6).

Major changes to the project schedule and project manpower plan must be confirmed by all affected parties, including the Coordinator. Failure to comply with the agreed project schedule and the respective consequences are regulated by the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement.

Figure 5
Periodic Reporting

Periodic Report: overview

TECHNICAL REPORT

1. **Part A: Continuous Reporting module on the platform** → next slide
It contains the structured tables with project information (retrieved from the Grant Management System).

2. **Part B: Narrative part**
- Prepared by all as a word document and submitted by the Coordinators PDF document
It must include:
* What was done and achieved?
* Which problems were encountered?
* How can progress so far be assessed?
* Were there any deviations or corrective actions?
* Delays, work not implemented, new subcontracts, budget overruns etc.

FINANCIAL REPORT

- Individual financial statements, prepared by all beneficiaries (and third parties) on the platform
- Detail the eligible costs for each budget category
- Explanation of the use of resources and information on subcontracting
- The certificates on the financial statements (CFS)

European Commission

Figure 6
Financial Reporting

Financial reporting: explanation on the use of resources

A. Personnel:

- Actual or unit costs
- Number of PM per WP
- Types: employees (or equivalent), natural persons, seconded persons, SME owners
- Amounts and description if in kind contribution from third parties

B. Subcontracting:

- Actually incurred in the period (as per Annex 1 and Annex 2)
- Beneficiary's usual purchasing practices
- Best value for money ↔ no conflict of interests
- Details to be provided

C. Purchase costs:

- Actually incurred in the period
- C.1 Travel & subsistence
- C.2 Equipment, infrastructure or other assets
- C.3 Other goods, works and services
- Explanation needed ONLY if amount > 15% of personnel
- Amounts and description if in kind contribution from third parties

D. Other cost categories:

- D.1 Financial support to third parties

European Commission

MeDeMAP – Mapping Media for Future Democracies

Deliverable 1.1

Version 2.0

(August 2024)

